

STUDIES IN VITAMIN C. PART V. THE VITAMIN C CONTENT OF SOME GERMINATED CEREALS AND PULSES.

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The vitamin C content of some germinated cereals and pulses has been determined by modified Tillmans method after reducing the trichloroacetic acid extract with H_2S . *Mung* has been found to synthesise the greatest amount (231.0 mg./100g. in 5 days) of vitamin C.

It is well known that germinated grains are good sources of vitamin C. Germinated Bengal gram and other pulses are often prescribed in cases of vitamin C deficiency. But for want of good quantitative data, the dosage can only be decided upon empirically. Ghosh and Guha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 30) tried to estimate the vitamin C content of germinated *mung* titrimetrically but, when tested biologically, the germinated *mung* was found to be considerably richer in vitamin C content. The obvious explanation is that the ascorbic acid synthesised in germinated grains is mostly in the form of the reversibly oxidised dehydroascorbic acid (*cf.* Lee and Read, *J. Chinese Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **4**, 208) which is biologically active but cannot be estimated by the reduction of 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol. The present investigation was undertaken to make a quantitative assay of the vitamin C content of germinated grains so that they may be prescribed with a knowledge of the amounts of their vitamin C content.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Tap water was used for germination in all these experiments. The grains (50-200 in number depending upon their weights) were taken in a beaker, weighed and washed in several changes of water. They were then soaked in water for 24 hours. After this period the water was drained away and the swollen grains were allowed to germinate. If during germination, the grains became too much dried up, they were again moistened with a little water. The number of days of germination was calculated from the time they were kept under water for soaking. The vitamin C content of the germinated grains was then estimated by a slightly modified method of the author described in a previous paper (*Biochem. J.*, 1936, **30**, 701). The germinated grains (10-30 depending upon their weight) were taken and their original weight before being soaked was calculated. They were then

extracted with 20% trichloroacetic acid and through the filtrate a moderate current of hydrogen sulphide was passed for 15 minutes. The container was then stoppered, wrapped in a piece of brown paper and kept in the dark for 24 hours. Next day the extract was again filtered through a dry filter and through the filtrate a rapid current of carbon dioxide was passed till it was completely free from hydrogen sulphide as tested with moist lead acetate paper. It was now titrated against 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol solution which was standardised with ascorbic acid solution which in its turn was standardised with iodine solution. The titrations were timed with a stop-watch. The vitamin C content synthesised was then calculated on the basis of the original weights of the grains in the dry state before they were soaked in water. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Total vitamin C content of germinated grains.

Name of grains.	Period of germination.	Length of radicals.	Vitamin C content (mg./100g.)
Barley (<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>)	3 days	2-4 mm.	19.5
"	5	6-10	31.1
Wheat (<i>Triticum vulgare</i>)	3	1-5	17.3
"	5	8-16	34.5
Bengal gram (<i>Cicer arietinum</i>)	2	2.5-5	40.7
"	3	5-15	44.9
"	4	10-20	50.6
"	5	15-25	68.5
Mung (<i>Phaseolus mungo</i>)	2	4-7	89.9
"	3	6-14	123.5
"	5	15-22	231.0

It thus appears that *mung* (green gram) can synthesise the largest amount of vitamin C, weight for weight, during germination. The cereals are capable of synthesising vitamin C to a lesser extent than the pulses. However, since the cereals can synthesise vitamin C to a considerable extent, it is of interest to find how much vitamin C, if any, is contained in malt extracts.

Malt is generally prepared by allowing barley and wheat to germinate for six days or more and then roasting the germinated grains and extracting

them. Unless all the vitamin C is destroyed during roasting, malt extract should be fairly abundant in vitamin C content. On examining a sample of concentrated extract of malt of a well known Calcutta firm, it was found that the total vitamin C content of the malt extract was 22.3 mg./100 g., whereas the vitamin C contents of wheat and barley after 5 days' germination only are 34.6 mg. and 31.1 mg. respectively. It would thus appear that some of the vitamin C is destroyed during the roasting process of the germinated grains in malting.

D I S C U S S I O N .

From the results it is apparent that the dicotyledons can synthesise relatively higher amounts of vitamin C than monocotyledons. As a result of the present investigation it would now be possible to prescribe germinated grains with a fair degree of accuracy about their vitamin C contents. It can be seen that 2 oz. of Bengal gram germinated for 2 days (23 mg. vitamin C) and 1 oz. of mung germinated for the same period (25.6 mg. vitamin C) would be sufficient to meet the daily vitamin C requirement of an adult. The relatively much higher vitamin C content of germinated mung raises the question if mung synthesises some other reducing substance besides ascorbic acid, especially as Johnson reports that germinated peas contain some other indophenol reagent-reducing substance than ascorbic acid (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 1942). The apparently high vitamin C content of germinated mung may be due to some other factor which is under investigation (*cf.* Rudra, *Nature*, 1938, 141, 203). Malt extracts contain a fair amount of vitamin C and, therefore, malt extracts combined with cod liver oil or halibut liver oil should contain the important vitamins A, B, C, and D. Manufacturers would do well to publish the vitamin C assay figures of their malt preparations along with the A, B, and D units content published by them. For similar considerations, malted whole milk should be comparatively richer in vitamin C content and would thus be more beneficial to scorbutic children than whole milk.

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